

A Study of the Reactivity of Bz-substituted 3,1,4-Benzoxazones. Part I. Synthesis of 2-Methyl- and 2-Phenyl-6 (& 7)-chloro- 4-ketoquinazolines

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The reactions of 6-chloro- and 7-chloro-2-methyl-3,1,4-benzoxazones and the corresponding 2-phenyl analogues with various amines, leading to the formation of the corresponding 4-ketoquinazolines, have been described.

The reactivity of a 3,1,4-benzoxazone, formed on refluxing an *N*-acylanthranilic acid with acetic anhydride, depends on the nature of the substituent in 2-position¹. Simple 3,1,4-benzoxazone deteriorates readily on keeping; its 2-aryl analogues can be preserved without its undergoing any deterioration. The 2-aryl analogues are stable. 2-Alkyl-3,1,4-benzoxazones react readily with amines, affording the corresponding 2-*N*-acylamiobenz-*N*-substituted amide or 2-alkyl-4-ketoquinazoline, depending on the reaction temperature.

2-Aryl-3,1,4-benzoxazone reacts with amine only at a higher temperature¹⁻³. So far no attempt has been made to ascertain the influence of Bz-substituents on the reactivity of the so-substituted 3,1,4-benzoxazone even though the 3,1,4-benzoxazone-amine reaction has been often used for the synthesis of Bz-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline.

1. Zentmeyer and Wagner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 667.

2. Lothrop and Goodwin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 363.

3. Levy and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 985.

With this aim in view, the present work dealing with the study of the reactivity of 2-methyl-6-chloro- and 2-methyl-7-chloro-benzoxazones and their 2-phenyl analogues was undertaken.

2-Methyl-6-chloro-(I), 2-methyl-7-chloro-(II), 2-phenyl-6-chloro-(III), and 2-phenyl-7-chloro (IV)-3, 1, 4-benzoxazones were formed on refluxing the required 5-chloro- or 4-chloro-*N*-acetyl- or *N*-benzoyl-anthranilic acid with acetic anhydride according to Zentmeyer and Wagner¹ with the modifications that a smaller amount of acetic anhydride was used, the refluxing period was decreased, and the product was isolated on cooling the reaction mixture and not by distilling the excess acetic anhydride under reduced pressure. The contact with acetic anhydride for a longer period may be the reason for the transacylation observed in some cases in this reaction^{1,4}. Compound (I) could be crystallised from dry solvents and could be preserved, but compound (II) on prolonged keeping was hydrolysed to the corresponding 4-chloro-*N*-acetylanthranilic acid. Products (III) and (IV) were found to be quite stable and were isolated unchanged when left in contact with water and even dilute ammonia solution at the room temperature.

Product (I) reacted respectively with ammonia, methylamine solution (20%) or ethanolic solution of benzylamine (10%) at 0°, and also at 30°, yielding the corresponding 5-chloro-2-acetaminobenz-*N*-substituted amide (V), and at 100°, affording the corresponding 3-substituted-2-methyl-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline (VI). Reaction of (I) with ammonia, leading to the formation of 2-methyl-3(*H*)-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline, has been reported⁵. Compound (I), when left in contact with ethanolic aniline (10%) at 0°, yielded 5-chloro-2-acetaminobenzanilide and at 30°, 2-methyl-3-phenyl-4-ketoquinazoline.

Product (II) condensed much more readily than (I) did respectively with ammonia, methylamine, and aniline at 0°, affording the corresponding 4-chloro-2-acetaminobenz-*N*-substituted amide and at the room temperature, it yielded the corresponding 3-substituted-2-methyl-4-ketoquinazoline.

Compounds (III) and (IV) did not react with ammonia and arylamines at the room temperature and were recovered from the reaction mixture; these condensed with the amines only at temperatures nearing 80° and above, yielding the corresponding 5-chloro- or 4-chloro-2-benzaminobenzamide or benzanilide, respectively. The same products were formed even when the reaction temperature was raised to 150°; the corresponding 3-substituted-6-chloro- or 7-chloro-2-phenyl-4-ketoquinazolines were not formed directly. The latter were formed by cyclodehydration of the corresponding 5-chloro- or 4-chloro-2-benzaminobenzamide or benzanilide by heating it at a temperature 10° higher than its melting point.

The cyclodehydration of 5-chloro- or 4-chloro-2-*N*-acylaminobenzamides, described above, could be effected by treating them with a hot dilute alkali solution.

These results suggest that the 3,1,4-benzoxazones (I, III, and IV) do not differ much in their reactivities from their corresponding simple 2-methyl or 2-phenyl-3,1,4-benzoxazones, but (II) having chlorine in a position *para* with respect to the benzoxazone carbonyl atom is more reactive.

4. Tomisek and Christenson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1701.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methyl-6-chloro-3, 1, 4-benzoxazone (I) was formed on refluxing 5-chloro-*N*-acetyl-anthranilic acid (4 g.) with acetic anhydride (6 ml) for about 10 min. The reaction mixture on cooling deposited needles which were collected and washed free of acetic anhydride with dry light petroleum; m.p. 123-25°, yield 3.0 g. The product was sufficiently pure for its use in the next operation. Tomisek and Christenson⁵ record the same m.p. (Found: N, 7.3. Calc. for C₉H₆O₂NCl: N, 7.2%).

2-Methyl-7-chloro-3,1,4-benzoxazone (II), obtained from 4-chloro-*N*-acetyl-anthranilic acid, as above, was crystallised from acetic anhydride in white needles⁶, m.p. 145°. (Found: N, 7.05. Calc. for C₉H₆O₂NCl: N, 7.20%).

2-Phenyl-6-chloro-3,1,4-benzoxazone (III) was synthesised from 5-chloro-*N*-benzoyl-anthranilic acid by following the same method as above. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m.p. 195-97°. (Found: N, 5.3. C₁₄H₉O₂NCl requires N, 5.4%).

2-Phenyl-7-chloro-3,1,4-benzoxazone (IV), obtained from 4-chloro-*N*-benzoyl-anthranilic acid, was crystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m.p. 192°. Heller and Hessel⁶, who obtained it by the action of benzoyl chloride on 4-chloroanthranilic acid, record m.p. as 198°. (Found: N, 5.25. Calc. for C₁₄H₉O₂NCl: N, 5.46%).

Reaction of Products (I, II, III or IV) with Ammonia or the Amines: General Methods.—The general procedures for the reactions of these benzoxazones with different amines have been described below. The details regarding the conditions of the reaction and the characteristics of the products are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
4-or 5-Chloro-2-(R-CO) aminobenz -N-(R')-substituted amide.

Compound No.	Product R'.	Made from Cl.	3,1,4-benz-oxazone.	Amine.	Reaction temp.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
								Found.	Reqd.
A. R=Me.									
1	H	5	I	NH ₃	30°	195-96°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	13.1	13.2
2	Me	5	I	CH ₃ NH ₂	30°	202-203°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.12	12.3
3	PhCH ₂	5	I	Ph.CH ₂ .NH ₂	30°	150°-57°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	8.9	9.2
4	Ph	5	I	Ph.NH ₂	0°	123-25°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	0.6	0.7
5	H	4	II	NH ₃	0°	201-202°	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.0	13.2
6	Me	4	II	CH ₃ NH ₂	0°	183-80°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.1	12.3
7	PhCH ₂	4	II	Ph.CH ₂ .NH ₂	0°	208-10°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.0	9.2
8	Ph	4	II	PhNH ₂	0°	106-108°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	9.5	9.7
B. R=Ph.									
9	H	5	III	NH ₃	100°	270-72°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	10.0	10.2
10	PhCH ₂	5	III	PhCH ₂ .NH ₂	"	167-66°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.4	7.7
11	Ph	5	III	PhNH ₂	"	225-26°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.8	8.0
12	<i>p</i> -OMePh	5	III	<i>p</i> -OMe.PhNH ₂	"	105-06°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.2	7.3
13	H	4	IV	NH ₃	"	230°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	10.0	10.2
14	Ph.CH ₂	4	IV	PhCH ₂ .NH ₂	"	182-83°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.5	7.7
15	Ph	4	IV	PhNH ₂	"	228-29°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.8	8.0
16	<i>p</i> -OMePh	4	IV	<i>p</i> -OMe.PhNH ₂	"	204-205°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	7.0	7.3

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2423.

6. Heller and Hessel, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1928, 120, 64.

7. Guenther and Morgan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 542.

Liquor ammonia (d 0.91), methylamine solution (20%), and 10% ethanolic solutions of benzylamine and the aromatic amine were used for these reactions.

TABLE II
6-(or 7)-Chloro-2-(R)-3-(R')-4-ketoquinazolines.

R'	Cl.	Methods.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
A. R=Me.						
H	6	B(I)* D(1)**	282-84(5)	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	14.20	14.40
Me	6	B(F) D(2)	151-52°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	13.10	13.40
PhCH ₂	6	B(I) D(3)	131-32°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	9.43	9.84
Ph	6	B(I) D(4)	180-81°(7)	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.10	10.35
H	7	C(II) D(5)	262-63°(6)	C ₉ H ₇ ON ₂ Cl	14.10	14.40
Me	7	C(II) D(6)	148-50°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	13.15	13.40
PhCH ₂	7	C(II) E(7)	115-10°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	10.05	9.84
Ph	7	C(II) E(8)	173-75°	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl	10.05	10.35
B. R=Ph.						
H	6	D & E(9)	294-95°	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	10.60	10.90
PhCH ₂	6	E(10)	116-18°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ NCI	7.80	8.00
Ph	6	E(11)	175-76°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	8.10	8.40
p-OMePh	6	E(12)	221-23°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.40	7.70
H	7	D(13)	292°	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl	10.60	10.90
Ph CH ₂	7	E(14)	91-93°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	7.80	8.00
Ph	7	E(15)	180-81°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl	8.20	8.42
p-OMePh	7	E(16)	150-52°	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.45	7.72

*The Roman letters I, II, III, & IV in parenthesis with the method number denote the 3, 1, 4-benzoxazone yielding the corresponding 4-ketoquinazoline directly on being allowed to react with an amine.

**The numerals in parenthesis with the method number indicate 2-acylaminobenzamide derivative (vide Table I) which has been cyclodehydrated.

Formation of 5-Chloro-or 4-Chloro-2-acylaminobenz-N-substituted Amide: Method A.—The required 3,1,4-benzoxazone derivative was finely suspended in five times the volume of liquor ammonia or the solution of the amine at 0°. It was then left at the required temperature overnight and diluted with excess of water (in case of reactions with aromatic amines with 5% HCl) and filtered. The solid was collected and treated thoroughly with dilute cold bicarbonate solution, filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from ethanol. In some cases the bicarbonate solution on acidification yielded the corresponding 5-chloro-or 4-chloro-N-acylanthranilic acid, formed due to hydrolysis of the benzoxazone.

2-Methyl-3(H) or (R)-6-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline: Direct Formation: Method B.—The reaction mixture, prepared as described above, was heated on a boiling water bath for 2 hr. The product obtained on working the reaction mixture as usual was crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methyl-3(H) or (R)-7-chloro-4-ketoquinazoline: Method C.—When the reaction was effected as described in method (A) at the room temperature, the products formed were crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methyl- or 2-Phenyl-3(H) or (Me)-6- or 7-chloro-4-ketquinazolines: Method D.—The required 5- or 4-chloro-2-acylamino benzamide derivative (1 g.), suspended in a 5% alkali solution (10 ml), was heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with acetic acid furnished the product. It was crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methyl or 2-Phenyl-3-(R)-6- or 7-chloro-4-ketquinazolines: Method E.—The required 5-chloro or 4-chloro-2-acylamino benz-*N*-substituted amide derivative was directly heated at 10° higher than its melting point for 15 min. The cooled residue was broken, extracted with acetic acid, and filtered after charcoal treatment. The product obtained on diluting the acetic acid extract with excess of water was crystallised from acetic acid or ethanol.

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